

1 **Discrete-time deterministic model for ocean**
2 **plastic waste management linked to GDP and**
3 **policy incentives**

4 *Preprint Version

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7 **Abstract**

8 This paper presents a new discrete-time deterministic model for managing ocean plastic
9 waste by incorporating the relationship between plastic waste generation, GDP growth, and
10 policy-driven recycling efforts. Extending previous models, we introduce terms that account for
11 GDP-influenced waste production and recycling improvements due to policy incentives. The
12 model analyzes the equilibrium points for two scenarios: a marine debris-free ocean and another
13 where the marine debris persists. Using Jury's stability conditions, we establish criteria for
14 system stability and derive the basic reproduction number (\mathcal{R}_0) to determine whether plastic
15 pollution will persist or decline. Additionally, a bifurcation analysis reveals the conditions
16 under which a transition occurs between equilibrium states, providing insights into the impact
17 of economic growth and policy measures on long-term plastic waste dynamics.

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1 Introduction

Ocean plastic pollution has escalated in recent decades as global plastic production now exceeds nearly 300 million tonnes per year, with single-use items (packaging, bags, etc.) accounting for over half of this total [1]. These disposables alone constitute an estimated 60–95% of visible coastal and floating marine litter. Studies estimate that in 2010 alone between 4.8 and 12.7 million tons of plastic were discharged into the ocean from land sources, a figure that is expected to increase dramatically in the coming decades if waste management practices remain inadequate [2]. Plastic waste persists in marine environments, breaking down into microplastics that pose threats to marine life and ecosystems [3]. Marine animals are particularly vulnerable to plastic pollution, as they can ingest plastic debris, mistaking it for food, or become entangled in it, leading to injury or death. Studies have shown that at least 267 marine species, including sea turtles, seabirds, and marine mammals, are affected by plastic pollution, either by ingestion or by entanglement [4]. Ingestion of plastics can reduce food intake, cause internal injuries, and lead to reproductive failure, while entanglement can hinder movement, impair feeding, or result in drowning [5–7]. Furthermore, plastics can act as a medium for the transport of toxic chemicals such as polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), which can accumulate in marine food chains and pose further risks to marine biodiversity [8, 9].

Plastics entering the sea come from diverse pathways: rivers carry land-based waste into gyres, while at sea sources (lost fishing and aquaculture gear, shipping debris, industrial effluents) are also significant. Reviews highlight that single use consumer plastics have dominated attention, but plastic waste from fishing also contributes substantially to ocean debris [10]. Likewise, trade-related dumping and industrial discharges are now recognized drivers of the marine plastic crisis [11]. Quantitative studies suggest that major rivers transfer on the order of 10^6 – 10^7 tonnes per year of plastic into oceans [12]. In offshore accumulation zones, individual large macro-debris items (e.g. nets, buoys) occur only sparsely (a few items per km^2) but represent a disproportionate fraction of floating plastic mass by weight [13]. Together, these findings portray a multifaceted, growing ocean-plastic problem driven by ubiquitous single-use polymers and compounded by marine industry activities.

Recent scientific and technical advances are rapidly improving how we monitor and manage ocean

1 plastics. Novel observational methods combine remote sensing and AI: for example, a neural-network
2 model was developed on thousands of ship-based images to automatically detect and map floating
3 macroplastics, finding results consistent with circulation models [13]. Drones and UAV surveys
4 have also been harnessed to develop a deep-learning (U-Net) algorithm to segment plastic from
5 high-resolution aerial imagery, achieving F1-scores of nearly 0.8–0.9 for different plastic types and
6 yielding reliable estimates of plastic area and volume [14]. In parallel, numerical models of plastic
7 transport have grown more sophisticated. For instance, calibrated hydrodynamic particle models
8 now simulate how land-sourced plastics enter oceans: a recent global analysis showed that roughly
9 1,000 rivers account for nearly 80 % of annual riverine plastic emissions (0.8–2.7 Mt/yr) [12]. On the
10 materials front, biodegradable polymer research has progressed: one novel film made of crosslinked
11 starch and cellulose remains intact in fresh water but rapidly dissolves in seawater (crosslinks break
12 under salinity), pointing to plastics that persist on land but disappear if lost to the ocean [15].
13 Finally, waste-interception technologies have scaled up. Remotely deployed trash-collection barriers
14 (e.g. river “Interceptors”) and ocean cleanup systems are being rolled out in many countries. (For
15 example, an international NGO reports plans to deploy barrier networks in 30 cities to remove up to
16 one-third of riverine plastics by 2030 [16]). These combined advances in remote detection, transport
17 modeling, new biodegradable materials, and cleanup hardware significantly enhance our ability to
18 quantify, target, and reduce ocean plastic waste.

19 Recognizing the urgency, governments at all levels are adopting plastic reduction policies and
20 best practices. Internationally, landmark agreements now target plastic flows: for example, in 2019
21 the Basel Convention amended its annexes to require consent for exports of most plastic waste [11],
22 and in 2022 the UN began negotiations on a legally binding Global Plastics Treaty. Many countries
23 and regions have enacted bans, fees, and producer-responsibility laws. The EU’s Single-Use Plastics
24 Directive (2021) forbids common items (straws, cutlery, polystyrene containers, etc.) and mandates
25 producer-paid waste schemes. Eight U.S. states have implemented Extended Producer Responsibility
26 (EPR) for packaging, forcing manufacturers to finance post-consumer recycling and waste manage-
27 ment [11]. Regional deposit-return systems now achieve >90% return rates for beverage containers
28 in countries like Germany and Norway. Evaluations show that such policies can yield large impacts:
29 well-designed bag levies and bans in Europe produced consumption drops on the order of 80–90%

1 (e.g. Ireland’s 2002 bag tax) [17]. However, experience also underscores shortcomings: one review
 2 found that plastic-bag bans alone had only “limited success” unless accompanied by enforcement
 3 and alternatives [17]. In other words, partial measures can be undermined by substitution or illegal
 4 trade. Crucially, many assessments note persistent gaps in both science and policy. On the model-
 5 ing side, most dynamic plastic budget models still treat policies as fixed inputs and lack economic
 6 feedback loops. As [18] argue, current models “cannot grasp” the complexity of source-to-sea flows
 7 and fail to integrate policy/economic drivers. This gap suggests a need for integrated frameworks
 8 that couple environmental transport with socio-economic behavior.

9 2 Governing Equations

10 We will use the system of difference equations for the formulation of the model. The model is
 11 divided into three compartments: plastic waste (W), marine debris (M), and recycled materials
 12 (R). Before giving the governing equations, we will first give a function that relates plastic waste
 13 generated with the GDP growth using the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) given as follows

$$G_n = P_n \exp(A + B \ln(Q_n) + C \ln(Q_n)^2 + DX_n + E_n) \quad (1)$$

14 where, the subscript n denotes the time step, P_n is the population size, Q_n is GDP per capita,
 15 X_n denotes the exogenous variable (including urbanization rate, government regulations, corruption
 16 levels, education levels), $B > 0$ and $C < 0$ are constants ensuring initial increase and later decrease
 17 respectively, and A, D, E_n are constants and error terms.

18 As GDP increases, governments typically have more financial resources to invest in recycling
 19 programs, waste management infrastructure, and environmental policies. Therefore, we introduce
 20 a term representing the amount of plastic recycled as a result of new infrastructure, policies, and
 21 waste management initiatives, apart from usual recycling, expressed as κIW_n . Here, κ indicates the
 22 effectiveness of incentives, how much they enhance recycling, while W_n represent the waste at time
 23 step n and I represent the new policy incentives.

1 The governing equations for three compartments of our system are given as follows

$$W_{n+1} = W_n + \lambda G_n - (\gamma + \kappa I)W_n - \beta M_n W_n + \mu R_n, \quad (2)$$

$$M_{n+1} = M_n + \beta M_n W_n - \alpha M_n, \quad (3)$$

$$R_{n+1} = R_n + (\gamma + \kappa I)W_n + \alpha M_n - (\mu + \theta)R_n, \quad (4)$$

2 where, W_k, M_k, R_k denotes plastic waste, marine debris and recycled material at time step k , λ rate
 3 of reproduction of new waste with increasing GDP, $\beta M_n W_n$ denotes the amount of waste converted
 4 into marine debris, γW_n denotes the natural recycling of waste, that gets recycled due to existing
 5 infrastructure and baseline policies, which is independent of external policies interventions, μR_n
 6 denotes the reproduction of new waste from the recycled material, αM_n denotes the marine debris
 7 that is recycled and θR_n denotes the recycled material that is lost due to inefficiencies, contamination,
 8 degradation, or other factors that prevent it from being reused.

9 **3 Equilibrium of the system**

10 At the steady state we will have $W_{n+1} = W_n = \tilde{W}$, $M_{n+1} = M_n = \tilde{M}$ and $R_{n+1} = R_n = \tilde{R}$.
 11 Hence the governing equations in the long term are given as follows.

$$\lambda G - (\gamma + \kappa I)\tilde{W} - \beta \tilde{M}\tilde{W} + \mu \tilde{R} = 0, \quad (5)$$

$$\beta \tilde{M}\tilde{W} - \alpha \tilde{M} = 0, \quad (6)$$

$$(\gamma + \kappa I)\tilde{W} + \alpha \tilde{M} - (\mu + \theta)\tilde{R} = 0, \quad (7)$$

14 where, G denotes GDP in long run. Now, from Equation (7) we can have two possibilities $\tilde{M} = 0$
 15 or $\tilde{M} \neq 0$.

1 3.1 Case 1 $\tilde{M} = 0$, no marine debris

2 If $\tilde{M} = 0$, then from Equations (6) and (8) we will have

$$\lambda G - (\gamma + \kappa I)\tilde{W} + \mu\tilde{R} = 0, \quad (8)$$

3

$$(\gamma + \kappa I)\tilde{W} - (\mu + \theta)\tilde{R} = 0. \quad (9)$$

4 Solving the above two equations for \tilde{R} and \tilde{W} gives the equilibrium point

$$EP_1 = \left(\frac{(\mu + \theta)\lambda G}{(\gamma + \kappa I)\theta}, 0, \frac{\lambda G}{\theta} \right). \quad (10)$$

5 3.2 Case 2, $\tilde{M} \neq 0$, waste is converted into marine debris

6 If $\tilde{M} \neq 0$ then from Equation (7), we have $\tilde{W} = \frac{\alpha}{\beta}$. Substituting the value of this \tilde{W} in Equations
7 (6) and (8) we get the equilibrium point in this case as

$$EP_2 = \left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta}, \frac{((\mu + \theta)\beta\lambda G - (\gamma + \kappa I)\theta\alpha)}{\alpha\theta\beta}, \frac{\lambda G}{\theta} \right). \quad (11)$$

8 4 Stability of the equilibrium points

9 First, we calculate the basic reproduction number, a key factor in understanding the behavior
10 of the compartmental model [19–22]. This value helps determine the long-term stability of the
11 system. It represents the average amount of marine debris generated when plastic waste enters a
12 clean ocean environment (a fully susceptible waste compartment). Essentially, it tells us whether
13 plastic pollution will persist and grow or disappear over time.

14 The Jacobian of the system in Equations (3) - (5) at $S = (M, W, R)$ is given as flows

$$J(S) = \begin{pmatrix} \beta W + (1 - \alpha) & \beta M & 0 \\ -\beta W & 1 - (\gamma + \kappa I + \beta M) & \mu \\ \alpha & \alpha + \kappa I & 1 - (\mu + \theta) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (12)$$

1 The Jacobian at the equilibrium point $EP_1 = (M^1, W^1, R^1)$, with no marine debris takes the form

$$J(EP_1) = \begin{pmatrix} \beta W^1 + (1 - \alpha) & 0 & 0 \\ -\beta W^1 & 1 - (\gamma + \kappa I) & \mu \\ \alpha & \alpha + \kappa I & 1 - (\mu + \theta) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (13)$$

2 Now, comparing $J(EP_1)$ with

$$J(EP_1) = \begin{pmatrix} \mathcal{F} + \mathcal{T} & 0 \\ \mathcal{A} & \mathcal{C} \end{pmatrix}, \quad (14)$$

3 we have

$$\mathcal{F} = \beta W^1, \quad \mathcal{T} = (1 - \alpha), \quad \mathcal{A} = \begin{pmatrix} -\beta W^1 \\ \alpha \end{pmatrix}, \quad \mathcal{C} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - (\gamma + \kappa I) & \mu \\ \gamma + \kappa I & 1 - (\mu + \theta) \end{pmatrix}. \quad (15)$$

4 Since the reproductive number \mathcal{R}_0 can be obtained as the spectral radius of $\mathcal{F}(1 - \mathcal{T})^{-1}$ [22, 23].

5 Hence using Equation (14) we have

$$\mathcal{R}_0 = \frac{\beta W^1}{\alpha} = \frac{\beta \lambda (\mu + \theta) G}{(\gamma + \kappa I) \theta \alpha}. \quad (16)$$

6 Based on the stability analysis we have the following two results with important implications on
7 policy matters.

8 **Result 1.** The marine debris-free equilibrium point always exists and it is asymptotically stable
9 if and only if $\mathcal{R}_0 < 1$ and $\frac{\kappa I (2 - \theta)}{\gamma \theta} < 1$.

10 From Equation (11), we know that $W^1 > 0$ and $R^1 > 0$; hence, the equilibrium point always
11 exists. Also, the eigen values of $J(EP_1)$ are $e_1 = \beta W^1 - (1 - \alpha)$ and eigen values of the matrix

$$12 \quad \mathcal{C} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - (\gamma + \kappa I) & \mu \\ \gamma + \kappa I & 1 - (\mu + \theta) \end{pmatrix}. \quad 13$$

14 Now, $|e_1| = e_1 < 1 \Leftrightarrow \beta W^1 - (1 - \alpha) < 1 \Leftrightarrow \frac{\beta W^1}{\alpha} < 1 \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{R}_0 < 1$.

15 According to the Jury's stability [24, 25], the matrix \mathcal{C} has eigen values with modulus less than 1 if

16 and only if $|tr(\mathcal{C})| < 1 + det(\mathcal{C}) < 2$.

1 Now,

$$2 \quad tr(\mathcal{C}) = 2 - (\gamma + \mu + \theta + \kappa I),$$

$$3 \quad det(\mathcal{C}) = 1 - (\gamma + \mu + \theta) - \kappa I(1 - \theta) + \gamma\theta, \text{ and}$$

$$4 \quad 1 + det(\mathcal{C}) = 2 - (\gamma + \mu + \theta) - \kappa I(1 - \theta) + \gamma\theta.$$

5 Since $\gamma, \theta < 1$, therefore, $-(\gamma + \theta) + \gamma\theta < 0$ and hence, $-(\gamma + \theta + \mu) + \gamma\theta < 0$, as $\mu > 0$ this will
 6 give us $-(\gamma + \theta + \mu) + \gamma\theta - \kappa I(1 - \theta) < 0$. Adding 2 on both side of the last expression we will have
 7 $2 - (\gamma + \theta + \mu) + \gamma\theta - \kappa I(1 - \theta) < 2 \Rightarrow 1 + det(\mathcal{C}) < 2$.

8 Now, $1 + det(\mathcal{C}) - tr(\mathcal{C}) = \gamma\theta + \kappa I\theta > 0 \Rightarrow tr(\mathcal{C}) < 1 + det(\mathcal{C})$, as $\gamma, \theta, \kappa I > 0$.

9 To show $|tr(\mathcal{C})| < 1 + det(\mathcal{C})$, it only remains to show $-(1 + det(\mathcal{C})) < tr(\mathcal{C})$, for this we consider
 10 $tr(\mathcal{C}) + 1 + det(\mathcal{C}) = 4 - 2(\gamma + \mu + \theta) - \kappa I(2 - \theta) + \gamma\theta$. Now, since $\gamma < 1 \Rightarrow -2\gamma > -2$ and
 11 $\mu + \theta < 1 \Rightarrow -2(\mu + \theta) > -2$, we have $4 - 2(\gamma + \mu + \theta) - \kappa I(2 - \theta) + \gamma\theta > -\kappa I(2 - \theta) + \gamma\theta$.

$$12 \quad \text{Now, } -\kappa I(2 - \theta) + \gamma\theta > 0 \Leftrightarrow \frac{\kappa I(2 - \theta)}{\gamma\theta} < 1 \Rightarrow 4 - 2(\gamma + \mu + \theta) - \kappa I(2 - \theta) + \gamma\theta > 0 \Leftrightarrow \frac{\kappa I(2 - \theta)}{\gamma\theta} < 1.$$

$$13 \quad \text{The last expression implies } -(1 + det(\mathcal{C})) < tr(\mathcal{C}) \Leftrightarrow \frac{\kappa I(2 - \theta)}{\gamma\theta} < 1.$$

14 Hence, $|tr(\mathcal{C})| < 1 + det(\mathcal{C}) \Leftrightarrow \frac{\kappa I(2 - \theta)}{\gamma\theta} < 1$, thus the result is concluded.

15 **Result 2.** If $\mathcal{R}_0 > 1$, the marine debris-included equilibrium point EP_2 exists and in addition
 16 it is asymptotically stable if and only if $1 < \mathcal{R}_0 < \frac{1}{(\gamma + \kappa I)} \left(\frac{8 - 4(\mu + \theta + \gamma + \kappa I) + 2(\gamma + \kappa I)\theta}{4 - 2(\mu + \alpha + \theta) + \alpha\theta} \right)$.

17 From Equation (12) we know the marine debris-included equilibrium point $EP_2 = (W^*, M^*, R^*)$,
 18 where $W^* > 0$ and $R^* > 0$ and M^* can be expressed as $\frac{(\gamma + \kappa I)}{\beta}(\mathcal{R}_0 - 1)$. Now, $M^* > 0$ if $\mathcal{R}_0 > 1$.
 19 Hence, EP_2 exists if $\mathcal{R}_0 > 1$.

20 The stability of EP_2 can be shown following the same steps followed for the Theorem (3.2) presented
 21 in [26].

22 5 Bifurcation analysis

23 Following bifurcation analysis we have the following two results with policy implications.

24 **Result 3.** The discrete model defined by Equations (2)- (4), has a transcritical/fold bifurcation
 25 if and only if $\mathcal{R}_0 = 1$.

26 For a discrete-time dynamical system, stability is determined by the eigenvalues of the Jacobian
 27 matrix at equilibrium [27, 28]. A fold bifurcation occurs when one eigenvalue crosses 1, leading to

1 the creation or destruction of equilibria. When an eigenvalue exactly equals 1, the equilibrium is in
 2 a critical state, meaning a small parameter change can cause two equilibria to collide or exchange
 3 stability.

4 At the marine debris-free equilibrium point EP_1 , we know eigen value $e_1 = \beta W^1 + 1 - \alpha = 1 \Leftrightarrow$
 5 $\beta W^1 = \alpha \Leftrightarrow \frac{\beta W^1}{\alpha} = 1 \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{R}_0 = 1$.

6 At marine debris-included equilibrium point EP_2 , we have the characteristic equation of the Jacobian
 7 matrix as $P(r) = r^3 + a_1 r^2 + a_2 r + a_3$, where $a_1 = -3 + x_1$, $a_2 = 3 - 2x_1 + x_2$, and $a_3 = -1 + x_1 - x_2 + x_3$,
 8 with $x_1 = \mu + \theta + \gamma + \kappa I + \beta M^*$, $x_2 = \beta M^*(\mu + \theta + \alpha) + (\gamma + \kappa I)\theta$, and $x_3 = \alpha \beta M^* \theta$.

9 Now, $e^* = 1$ is the eigen value of Jacobian matrix at EP_2 if 1 is the zero of characteristic polynomial
 10 $P(r)$, i.e., $P(1) = 0$, therefore $P(1) = 1 + a_1 + a_2 + a_3 = x_3 = 0 \Leftrightarrow \alpha \beta M^* \theta = 0$. Now, since
 11 $M^* = \frac{(\mu + \theta)\beta \lambda G - (\gamma + \kappa I)\theta \alpha}{\alpha \theta \beta}$ and $\mathcal{R}_0 = \frac{\beta \lambda G(\mu + \theta)}{(\gamma + \kappa I)\theta \alpha}$, we have $\beta M^* = (\mathcal{R}_0 - 1)(\gamma + \kappa I)$. Hence, $\alpha \beta M^* \theta =$
 12 $0 \Leftrightarrow \alpha \theta (\gamma + \kappa I)(\mathcal{R}_0 - 1) = 0$, since $0 < \theta, (\gamma + \kappa I), \alpha < 1$, therefore $P(1) = 0 \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{R}_0 = 1$.

13 **Result 4.** The system possesses only forward bifurcation.

14 From Result 1 we know the marine debris-free equilibrium point EP_1 exists if and only if $\mathcal{R}_0 < 1$.

15 Now, from Result 2 we know if $\mathcal{R}_0 > 1$ then marine debris-included equilibrium point EP_2 exists.

16 Now, from Result 3 we know $M^* = \frac{(\mathcal{R}_0 - 1)(\gamma + \kappa I)}{\beta}$, we can say $M^* > 0 \Leftrightarrow \mathcal{R}_0 > 1$. which means no
 17 endemic equilibrium exists for $\mathcal{R}_0 < 1$, this strongly suggests a forward bifurcation.

18 Our model admits two long-run regimes:

19 **Debris-free equilibrium EP_1 :** In this regime, marine debris tends to zero while waste and
 20 recycling settle to finite levels. EP_1 exists for all parameters and is asymptotically stable when
 21 $\mathcal{R}_0 < 1$ and $\frac{\kappa I(2 - \theta)}{\gamma \theta} < 1$. Intuitively, the combined generation to debris pathway is weak enough and
 22 the recycling subsystem is sufficiently well damped that leakage does not sustain an ocean stock of
 23 plastics.

24 **Debris-included equilibrium EP_2 :** When $\mathcal{R}_0 > 1$, the system stabilizes at a positive de-
 25 bris level $M^* = \frac{(\mu + \theta)\beta \lambda G - (\gamma + \kappa I)\theta \alpha}{\alpha \theta \beta}$. EP_2 appears exactly when EP_1 loses stability, via a forward
 26 bifurcation at $\mathcal{R}_0 = 1$, debris persistence is structurally favored.

27 Also note that the quantity $\mathcal{R}_0 = \frac{\beta \lambda G(\mu + \theta)}{(\gamma + \kappa I)\theta \alpha}$ summarizes the competition between debris-generating
 28 forces and debris-removal capacity. The numerator combines the factors that add debris: how much
 29 waste is produced for each unit of economic activity (λ), the size of the economy (G), the share

1 of waste that escapes to the ocean (β) and losses or extra waste from inefficiencies (μ, θ). The
2 denominator combines factors that remove or prevent debris: the basic recycling rate (γ), the extra
3 improvement from incentives (κI), the efficiency of recovering materials (θ), and the rate of debris
4 removal from the ocean (α). If $\mathcal{R}_0 < 1$, removal and prevention are strong enough to outweigh
5 new inputs, and debris will eventually disappear. If $\mathcal{R}_0 > 1$, new inputs are stronger than control
6 measures, and debris will settle at a permanent, non-zero level. This means the policy goal is simple:
7 make changes that push \mathcal{R}_0 below 1 by cutting waste production and leakage, improving recycling,
8 and increasing debris removal.

9 Overall, each parameter provides a concrete point of intervention for policymakers. The structure
10 of \mathcal{R}_0 makes it clear that achieving and maintaining $\mathcal{R}_0 < 1$ requires both reducing the rates of
11 waste generation and leakage (numerator terms) and enhancing the rates of recycling and removal
12 (denominator terms). In practice, the most robust strategy is a portfolio approach that targets
13 multiple parameters simultaneously, thereby reducing the system's sensitivity to fluctuations in any
14 single factor.

15 6 Remarks

16 The basic reproduction number \mathcal{R}_0 serves as a crucial indicator of whether marine debris will
17 persist or be eliminated. If $\mathcal{R}_0 < 1$, the system stabilizes at a marine debris-free state. However,
18 when $\mathcal{R}_0 > 1$, marine debris continues to accumulate, highlighting the need for stringent waste
19 management measures to keep \mathcal{R}_0 below the critical threshold. Also, Theorem 1 highlights that
20 policy-driven recycling incentives (κI) play a critical role in maintaining stability, but their effec-
21 tiveness depends on existing infrastructure efficiency (γ) and recycling losses (θ). When the basic
22 reproduction number crosses a threshold (from below 1 to above 1), a bifurcation occurs, leading
23 to a shift from a stable, debris-free equilibrium to one where marine debris persists. This finding is
24 critical for understanding long-term transitions in waste accumulation and the tipping points that
25 must be avoided.

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8 References

- 9 [1] Y.-I. Hsu, "Development of functional degradable materials by precise crosslinking design of
10 biobased polymers," *Polymer Journal*, pp. 1–11, 2025.
- 11 [2] J. R. Jambeck, R. Geyer, C. Wilcox, T. R. Siegler, M. Perryman, A. Andrady, R. Narayan,
12 and K. L. Law, "Plastic waste inputs from land into the ocean," *Science*, vol. 347, no. 6223,
13 pp. 768–771, 2015.
- 14 [3] A. L. Andrady, "Persistence of plastic litter in the oceans," *Marine Anthropogenic Litter*, pp. 57–
15 72, 2015.
- 16 [4] D. W. Laist, "Impacts of marine debris: entanglement of marine life in marine debris including
17 a comprehensive list of species with entanglement and ingestion records," in *Marine Debris:
18 Sources, Impacts, and Solutions*, pp. 99–139, Springer, 1997.
- 19 [5] P. Ryan, A. Connell, and B. Gardner, "Plastic ingestion and pcbs in seabirds: is there a
20 relationship?," *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 174–176, 1988.
- 21 [6] P. Ryan, "Effects of ingested plastic on seabird feeding: evidence from chickens," *Marine Pol-
22 lution Bulletin*, vol. 19, no. 3, pp. 125–128, 1988.
- 23 [7] C. W. Fowler, "Marine debris and northern fur seals: a case study," *Marine Pollution Bulletin*,
24 vol. 18, no. 6, pp. 326–335, 1987.

- 1 [8] Y. Mato, T. Isobe, H. Takada, H. Kanehiro, C. Ohtake, and T. Kaminuma, “Plastic resin pellets
2 as a transport medium for toxic chemicals in the marine environment,” *Environmental Science*
3 *& Technology*, vol. 35, no. 2, pp. 318–324, 2001.
- 4 [9] J. G. Derraik, “The pollution of the marine environment by plastic debris: a review,” *Marine*
5 *Pollution Bulletin*, vol. 44, no. 9, pp. 842–852, 2002.
- 6 [10] L. Apete, O. V. Martin, and E. Iacovidou, “Fishing plastic waste: Knowns and known un-
7 knowns,” *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, vol. 205, p. 116530, 2024.
- 8 [11] Z. Hui, A. Haider, and A. Khan, “International trade and plastic waste in oceans: Legal and
9 policy challenges,” *Frontiers in Marine Science*, vol. 12, p. 1627829.
- 10 [12] L. J. Meijer, T. Van Emmerik, R. Van Der Ent, C. Schmidt, and L. Lebreton, “More than 1000
11 rivers account for 80% of global riverine plastic emissions into the ocean,” *Science advances*,
12 vol. 7, no. 18, p. eaaz5803, 2021.
- 13 [13] R. De Vries, M. Egger, T. Mani, and L. Lebreton, “Quantifying floating plastic debris at sea
14 using vessel-based optical data and artificial intelligence,” *Remote Sensing*, vol. 13, no. 17,
15 p. 3401, 2021.
- 16 [14] G. Jakovljevic, M. Govedarica, and F. Alvarez-Taboada, “A deep learning model for automatic
17 plastic mapping using unmanned aerial vehicle (uav) data,” *Remote Sensing*, vol. 12, no. 9,
18 p. 1515, 2020.
- 19 [15] N. A.-H. K. Hussein, X. Huang, X. Li, and J. Yao, “Assessing the impact of circular economy
20 practices on global waste management systems,” *ESTIDAMAA*, vol. 2024, pp. 22–29, 2024.
- 21 [16] “The ocean cleanup launches 30 cities program to cut ocean plastic pollution from rivers by
22 one third by 2030 [https://theoceancleanup.com/updates/the-ocean-cleanup-launches-30-cities-
23 program-to-cut-ocean-plastic-pollution-from-rivers-by-one-third-by-2030/](https://theoceancleanup.com/updates/the-ocean-cleanup-launches-30-cities-program-to-cut-ocean-plastic-pollution-from-rivers-by-one-third-by-2030/), author=Cleanup,
24 The Ocean, journal=The Ocean Cleanup , volume=1, number=1, pages=1, year=2025,
25 publisher=The Ocean Cleanup,”

-
- 1 [17] A. Muposhi, M. Mpinganjira, and M. Wait, “Considerations, benefits and unintended con-
2 sequences of banning plastic shopping bags for environmental sustainability: A systematic
3 literature review,” *Waste Management & Research*, vol. 40, no. 3, pp. 248–261, 2022.
- 4 [18] N. O. Baci, F. L. Santiago-Collazo, C. B. Woodson, and J. R. Jambeck, “Advancing numerical
5 models for land-to-ocean litter transport: A review of hydrodynamic processes and inland
6 contributions,” *Science of The Total Environment*, vol. 970, p. 179013, 2025.
- 7 [19] M. Cordier, T. Uehara, J. Baztan, B. Jorgensen, and H. Yan, “Plastic pollution and economic
8 growth: The influence of corruption and lack of education,” *Ecological Economics*, vol. 182,
9 p. 106930, 2021.
- 10 [20] P. Van den Driessche and J. Watmough, “Reproduction numbers and sub-threshold en-
11 demic equilibria for compartmental models of disease transmission,” *Mathematical Biosciences*,
12 vol. 180, no. 1-2, pp. 29–48, 2002.
- 13 [21] P. Van den Driessche and J. Watmough, “Further notes on the basic reproduction number,”
14 *Mathematical Epidemiology*, pp. 159–178, 2008.
- 15 [22] P. Van den Driessche, “Reproduction numbers of infectious disease models,” *Infectious Disease*
16 *Modelling*, vol. 2, no. 3, pp. 288–303, 2017.
- 17 [23] O. Diekmann, J. A. P. Heesterbeek, and M. G. Roberts, “The construction of next-generation
18 matrices for compartmental epidemic models,” *Journal of The Royal Society Interface*, vol. 7,
19 no. 47, pp. 873–885, 2010.
- 20 [24] E. I. Jury, “Stability of multidimensional scalar and matrix polynomials,” *Proceedings of the*
21 *IEEE*, vol. 66, no. 9, pp. 1018–1047, 2005.
- 22 [25] L. J. Allen, “An introduction to mathematical biology,” *Pearson/Prentice Hall*,, 2007.
- 23 [26] M. Parsamanesh and M. Gümüş, “Qualitative study for the system of waste plastic management
24 in the ocean: A discrete-time deterministic model,” *Communications in Nonlinear Science and*
25 *Numerical Simulation*, p. 108617, 2025.

-
- 1 [27] C. Pötzsche, “Bifurcations in a periodic discrete-time environment,” *Nonlinear Analysis: Real*
2 *World Applications*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 53–82, 2013.
- 3 [28] L. Fei, X. Chen, and B. Han, “Bifurcation analysis and hybrid control of a discrete-time
4 predator–prey model,” *Journal of Difference Equations and Applications*, vol. 27, no. 1, pp. 102–
5 117, 2021.